

Viscometric investigations of uranyl soap solutions at different temperatures

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Abstract : The viscosity results of uranyl soaps in dimethyl formamide have been explained in terms of the equations proposed by Einstein, Vand, Moulik and Jones-Dole. The values of the cmc, molar volume and various constants calculated from these equations are in close agreement. The effect of chain length and temperature on the property is discussed. The viscosity results have been analysed on the basis of kinetic theory of viscosity of liquids.

Keywords : Viscosity, uranyl soap.

In spite of their considerable industrial applications the physico-chemical properties and structure of lanthanide and actinide soaps have not yet been investigated properly¹. The present paper deals with the studies of viscometric investigation of solutions of uranyl soaps at various temperatures.

Experimental

B.D.H. grade chemicals were used for the preparation of uranyl soaps (butyrate, valerate, caproate, caprylate). The soaps were prepared by the direct metathesis of corresponding potassium soap with required amount of aqueous solution of uranyl nitrate at 50–55 °C with vigorous stirring and were purified by recrystallization process. The purity of the soaps was checked by elemental analysis, IR spectroscopy and by determination of their melting points. The solution of uranyl soaps were prepared by dissolving requisite amount of soap in DMF solution.

The viscosity of the solutions of soaps at various temperatures (30, 40, 50, 60 °C) was measured by Ostwald's viscometer in a thermostat.

Results and discussion

The viscosity (η) of the uranyl soaps (butyrate, valerate, caproate and caprylate) in DMF increases with increase in the soap concentration as well as with the chain length of the soap but decreases with increase in temperature. The plots of viscosity (η) against the soap concentration are characterised by intersection of two straight lines at a definite soap concentration which corresponds to the cmc (critical micelle concentration) of the soaps (Fig. 1, for butyrate) (Table 1). The results show that the values of the cmc vary with the chain length of the anion

Table 1. Values of cmc $\times 10^2$ (mol dm⁻³) for various soaps

Soaps	Temperature (°C)			
	30°	40°	50°	60°
Butyrate	4.9	5.5	6.2	6.6
Valerate	4.3	5.2	5.9	5.9
Caproate	3.8	4.2	4.8	5.2
Caprylate	3.5	4.1	4.3	4.6

in the soap molecule and with temperature. The cmc decreases with the increase of chain length of hydrocarbon chain and increases with increase in temperature. This may be due to increase in the stability of the micelles as well as due to increase in tendency of aggregation and vice-versa. The values of cmc are in close agreement with the values obtained from conductivity and ultrasonic measurements.

The viscosity results are satisfactorily explained on the basis of following equations :

$$\text{Einstein}^2 : \eta_{sp} = 2.5 \bar{V} C \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Vand}^3 : \frac{1}{C} = \left[\frac{0.921}{V} \right]^{-1} \frac{1}{\log (\eta / \eta_0)} + \phi \bar{V} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Moulik}^4 : (\eta / \eta_0)^2 = M + K' C^2 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Jones-Dole}^5 : (\eta_{sp} / C^{1/2}) = A + B C^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

where η , η_0 , η_{sp} , \bar{V} , C and ϕ are viscosity of the solution, viscosity of the solvent, specific viscosity, molar volume of the soaps, concentration of the soap and interaction coefficient, respectively. M and K' are Moulik's constants and A and B refer to the soap-soap and soap-solvent interactions, respectively.

Note

Fig. 1. Viscosity vs concentration plots for uranyl butyrate at various temperatures : (■) 30 °C, (▲) 40 °C, (○) 50 °C, (△) 60 °C.

Table 2. Values of molar volume, \bar{V} and interaction coefficient, ϕ

Soaps	Temp. (°C)	\bar{V}		ϕ
		Einstein's eq.	Vand's eq.	
Butyrate	30	0.63	0.82	10.86
	40	0.54	0.6	9.54
	50	0.48	0.5	7.32
	60	0.42	0.48	6.79
Valerate	30	0.85	1.4	9.68
	40	0.71	1.37	7.32
	50	0.68	1.28	6.45
	60	0.62	1.24	5.96
Caproate	30	1.02	1.42	1.41
	40	0.97	1.38	1.32
	50	0.82	1.29	1.11
	60	0.76	1.25	1.09
Caprylate	30	1.26	1.45	0.98
	40	1.02	1.32	0.57
	50	0.98	1.35	0.32
	60	0.92	1.21	0.29

The values of the molar volume of the soap, \bar{V} , have been calculated from the slope of the plots of η_{sp} vs C (Einstein's equation) and from the plots of $1/C$ vs $1/\log(\eta/\eta_0)$ (Vand's equation). It is observed that the values of molar volume, \bar{V} obtained from these equations increase with chainlength of soaps while decrease with increasing temperature.

The values of constant M obtained from the plots of $(\eta/\eta_0)^2$ vs C^2 (Moulik's equation) are almost same for all the soaps at various temperatures (Table 3) which confirm that this equation is applicable to these soap solutions. The values of constant K' decrease with increase in temperature and increase with increase in chainlength of soaps.

Table 3. Values of constant M and K' (from Moulik's equation) and of A and B (from Jones-Dole's equation)

Soaps	Temp. (°C)	M	K'	A	B
Butyrate	30	1.05	48	0.008	1.4
	40	1.04	36	0.006	1.38
	50	1.04	22	0.004	1.35
	60	1.02	20	0.003	1.3
Valerate	30	1.06	70	0.103	1.7
	40	1.05	66	0.102	1.68
	50	1.05	63	0.1	1.65
	60	1.03	61	0.008	1.63
Caproate	30	1.06	85	0.104	1.95
	40	1.06	81	0.103	1.92
	50	1.05	78	0.101	1.9
	60	1.04	74	0.009	1.86
Caprylate	30	1.08	110	0.105	2.55
	40	1.07	109	0.104	2.48
	50	1.06	91	0.102	2.41
	60	1.05	90	0.1	2.34

The values of A and B constant calculated from the intercept and slope of Jones-Dole's plots below the cmc for uranyl soaps are recorded in Table 3. The values of coefficient B (soap-solvent interaction) are larger than the values of A (soap-soap interaction) which confirm that the molecules of the soap do not aggregate appreciably below the cmc.

The viscosity results have also been analysed on the basis of kinetic theory of viscosity of liquids⁶. The following expression may be used for the soap solutions,

$$\eta_{cmc} = N e^{E/RT} \quad (5)$$

where N and E are constant, T is the absolute tempera-

ture, R the universal gas constant, η_{cmc} is the viscosity of the soap solutions at cmc. Therefore, a plot of $\log \eta_{\text{cmc}}$ against $1/T$ results in a straight line, which yields N as intercept and E/R as slope. The values of N and E for uranyl soaps are given in Table 4. According to the ki-

Table 4. Constant N and E (kinetic equation)

Soaps	N	E
Butyrate	-1.04	0.053
Valerate	-1.07	0.056
Caproate	-1.10	0.058
Caprylate	-1.16	0.063

netic theory of liquids, the constant N depends on the packing characteristics of molecules and the molar volume. N is inversely proportional to molar volume and hence the values of N decrease with the increase in chain length. On the other hand, constant E depends on charac-

teristic free energy which may be related to the internal energy of the solution and the values increase with increase in chain length of the soaps.

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